

Startup Essentials

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Keywords

Business, Entrepreneurship, Financial Management, Human Resource Management, Innovation Management, Investment, Marketing, Project Management, Strategic Decision-making

Figure 1. Screenshot from *Startup Essentials* (TOPSIM GmbH). Used for educational review. Rights remain with the creators.

Introduction

The *Startup Essentials* simulation models the founding and management of a company using the example of a surfboard manufacturer. The thematic focus lies on the essential steps of starting a business—from ideation to business model development and financial and strategic planning. The goal is to convey economic relationships in a practical way and promote entrepreneurial thinking.

The primary target groups include students in business-related programs, founders, and professionals seeking to improve their business decision-making skills. As a serious game, *Startup Essentials* combines playful elements with a realistic learning approach, fostering interactive, application-oriented knowledge transfer.

The game is based on a step-by-step decision-making process: Participants analyze market conditions, make financing decisions, and develop management strategies. The simulation was released in 2017 by TOPSIM GmbH and has been continuously developed since then.

Facts

Release date:	Initial cloud release: Version 1.0 (2017). Current version: 5.1.0 (26.06.2024)
Developer:	TOPSIM GmbH
Game type:	Digital hybrid (at least one player per team requires internet access)
Number of players:	The number of players is infinitely scalable.
Format:	Asynchronous, Hybrid
Time frame:	Approx. 10–24 hours depending on how many of the six periods are played, how the simulation is conducted, and whether evaluations or additional tasks are included. Time and effort also depend on the intended learning objectives.
Languages:	English, German
Environment:	Device: Tablet, PC, or laptop (minimum 720p). Browsers: Chrome, Firefox, or Safari. Internet access required.
Material:	Participants receive an introduction, a participant handbook, business news, and seminar materials. The facilitator gets a seminar leader's handbook. Short description: https://www.topsim.com/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/Startup_Essentials_Flyer.pdf ; Blog article: https://www.topsim.com/blog/von-der-existenzgruendung-zur-unternehmensfuehrung-mit-startup-essentials/
Price:	TOPSIM simulations are fee-based. Licensing costs depend on the simulation, number of participants, and usage model. Direct inquiry with TOPSIM is recommended.

Resonance & Criticism

Startup Essentials allows participants to experience the typical steps of business creation without risk and to run a virtual company. No precise user numbers or detailed distribution statistics are currently publicly available. Its integration into university curricula and the frequent use of facilitator training programs suggest that the simulation is mainly used in teaching and professional development. Overall, Startup Essentials appears to be perceived as an innovative teaching tool in entrepreneurship education, though further evaluation is needed.

Game Principle & Process

In Startup Essentials, participants go through up to six simulated fiscal years (periods), during which they complete the stages of starting a business—from developing an idea and creating a business and financial plan to operational company management.

Teams use the specially developed “Startup Web” platform for market research, create a complete business plan using the business plan tool, and pitch it to virtual investors or the

seminar leader to secure financing. In each round, they make up to 14 decisions across sales, research & development, procurement, finance & accounting, production, and human resources.

In the TOPSIM Cloud—the digital learning platform of TOPSIM—they monitor simulated market reactions in real time. Continuous feedback through dynamic reports and KPI charts enables participants to reflect on and adjust their strategies in short cycles. Economic news keeps them informed of changing market conditions. Moderation analyses show that learners benefit most in serious-game settings when they work in teams, repeat the intervention, and combine gameplay with traditional teaching (Wouters et al., 2013).

The simulation's structured design provides complete decision control and, through teamwork under time pressure, strengthens communication and problem-solving skills. To prepare instructors to lead the simulation, TOPSIM offers a full-day (8-hour) live webinar facilitator training and recommends approximately 4 hours of self-study using the handbook and demo scenario.

Learning Objectives & Educational Fields of Application

Startup Essentials develops business competencies by guiding participants through the phases of starting and running a company. The focus lies on the ability to manage complex entrepreneurial situations. Learners analyze market information, identify demand potential and competitive advantages, and design a viable business model. With support from a business plan assistant, they develop a structured plan incorporating market analysis, financing strategies, and operational implementation.

A key aspect of the simulation is capital acquisition. Participants compare financing options and practice negotiation skills through dialogues with investors. After securing funding, they run the company and make decisions in production, marketing, and personnel management. The simulation enables them to develop strategies, consider economic conditions, and use company data to inform decision-making.

Teamwork plays a central role. Participants make decisions under time pressure, improving teamwork, communication, and problem-solving skills—mirroring real entrepreneurial challenges. Instructors accompany the simulation, introduce the process, and guide reflection phases. One instructor is generally sufficient to supervise multiple teams.

The game's mechanics support learning objectives through practical decision-making, real-time feedback, and a realistic market simulation. The immediate responses to decisions deepen understanding of economic relationships. Combining strategic planning, capital negotiation, and market analysis makes Startup Essentials particularly valuable for business education and prepares participants for entrepreneurial challenges.

Effectiveness

No specific studies on Startup Essentials have been conducted yet. However, practice reports and external research support the effectiveness of entrepreneurial simulations. A report on its use at Business School Stegersbach highlights that the practical design makes economic content tangible and encourages active engagement with business strategies (TOPSIM GmbH, 2021).

A quasi-experimental study by Sofiullah et al. (2023) demonstrated that online business simulations significantly improve entrepreneurial self-confidence, knowledge, and skills in university students. According to Samašonok et al. (2020), participants also reported improvements in leadership, management, and entrepreneurial competencies following simulation-based training.

The meta-analysis by Wouters et al. (2013) further found that serious games enhance motivation and flow experience through interactive elements and immediate feedback. These findings support the conclusion that Startup Essentials can be an effective tool in entrepreneurship education.

Potentially Problematic Aspects

Startup Essentials teaches business decision-making processes realistically and refrains from including problematic content such as violence, addiction, or discriminatory depictions. The simulation of business creation enables practical learning without relying on stereotypes or distressing topics. The challenges of entrepreneurial risk and financing decisions may be demanding, but they foster a deeper understanding of economic relationships. Basic business knowledge is advantageous for optimal participation. Individuals with visual or motor impairments may encounter barriers in the digital environment.

Reviewer(s): Hannes Hamester

Sources

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